
CETB Snow Water Equivalent

User Documentation

Version 1.0

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1 Preface

1.1 Purpose of this Document

This document describes Snow Water Equivalent files derived from the Calibrated Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature (CETB) Earth System Data Record (ESDR) product (Brodzik et al., 2016). SWE data are available for the complete historical record of the CETBv1 data, and updated for currently operating SSMIS sensors in near real-time (approximately 1–2 days from acquisition). The complete data record (including all intermediate processing outputs) is available via FTP. Selected processing output, at 3.125 km and 25 km spatial resolution, for daily SWE by sensor and daily composite (maximum, "last in" for all sensors operating on a given date) SWE is available by Web Coverage Service (WCS).

The current version of input *EASE-Grid 2.0* CETB data is version 1.x. The complete input data record is currently being reprocessed at the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC); when CETBv2 reprocessing is complete, the SWE data will be updated to use the new version of inputs.

This document includes the following sections: the remainder of Section 1 describes the intended users of this document and includes links to related detailed documents and the document revision history; Section 2 lists the passive microwave sensors and availability timeline, the SWE algorithm that is used, and short descriptions of the stages of SWE processing and compositing; Section 3 includes SWE file content and filename convention; Section 4 describes FTP and WCS access methods, and which parts of the data are available by each access method; Section 5 includes assumptions and limitations of SWE data; Section 6 includes funding acknowledgements for the project.

1.2 Who Should Use this Document

The intended readers of this document are those interested in a) understanding the contents of the various SWE data files, b) understanding how to access the data via WCS, and c) understanding what is served by FTP vs. WCS.

1.3 Related Documents

Details on the NSIDC1 SWE algorithm are included in Armstrong and Brodzik (2001). The CETBv1 data are available from the NSIDC DAAC (Brodzik et al., 2016). The rSIR algorithm, used to enhance the spatial resolution of passive microwave data for CETBv1, is described in Brodzik and Long (2018) and Long and Brodzik (2016). Changes that are planned for inclusion in CETBv2 processing are described in Brodzik et al. (2023).

1.4 Revision History

Table 1: Document Revision History

Revision	Date	Purpose
0.1	2024-04-15	Initial Draft Revision
1.0	2024-09-06	First Public Release

2 Introduction

2.1 Overview

Snow water equivalent images are derived from input gridded passive microwave (CETBv1) data using the *NSIDC1* SWE algorithm as defined by Armstrong and Brodzik (2001). The SWE historical record, from 1987 to present, includes data from 6 SSM/I (DMSP-F08, -F10, -F11, -F13, -F14, -F15) and 4 SSMIS (DMSP-F16, -F17, -F18, -F19) for operational periods illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Time series of CETBv2 SSM/I-SSMIS passive microwave sensors. Sensors labeled with ">>>" are still operating as of September 2024. Dates are approximate. SWE generated for SSM/I and SSMIS sensors only (rendered in color). Additional sensors (rendered in grey) are available as CETBv2, and could be considered for future inclusion in SWE products.

2.2 SWE Algorithm

The *NSIDC1* algorithm relies on the frequency-dependent temperature gradient in passive microwave brightness temperatures with increasing volume scattering. As snow depth increases, brightness temperatures at 37 GHz are more sensitive to volume scattering than those at 19 GHz. Armstrong and Brodzik (2001) define the difference between observations from these SSM/I channels at horizontal polarizations to be proportional to the water equivalent in the snow pack, as:

$$SWE = 1.59 * ((T_{B19H} - 6) - (T_{B37H} - 1)) \quad (1)$$

with T_{B19H} and T_{B37H} in Kelvins, and SWE in mm. A generalized conversion to snow depth

Figure 2: Land cover classification mask used for SWE files (Brodzik and Knowles, 2011).

in cm can be made using a simplified assumption of uniform density of 300 kg/m^3 , by multiplying SWE(mm) by a factor of 3.

The implementation of the NSIDC1 SWE algorithm enforces a lower threshold of SWE $< 7.5 \text{ mm}$, setting SWE = 0 when this threshold is reached. Grody and Basist (1996) described additional scattering surfaces (deserts) or conditions (convective storms producing heavy precipitation). The algorithm filters most false positives from these conditions by using a monthly climatology of snow cover (1966-2017) derived from Brodzik and Armstrong (2013). The SWE algorithm result is only reported for land surfaces, with other reasonably permanent surface types (ocean, glaciers and ice sheets, off-grid locations at projection corners) masked using Brodzik and Knowles (2011).

2.2.1 Daily SWE Files

For each sensor available on a given date, NSIDC1 SWE output is generated as a geolocated TIF image, using morning pass CETBv1 T_B images. Sensor coverage is not complete for the input time period (daily, morning passes only), which results in temporally similar "local-time-of-day" observations (Brodzik and Long, 2018), but incomplete spatial coverage (left column, Figure 3).

2.2.2 Daily "Last-in" SWE Files

To produce a time series of continuous, daily, SWE maps for the time period of each sensor lifetime, image composites are produced. For each sensor available on a given date, NSIDC1 SWE daily output are composited on a "last in" basis. At a given pixel, the most recent observation is used. Some data in the image will be older than the date of the image file,

but the image will provide a complete, "reasonably recent," area of SWE coverage (middle column, Figure 3).

2.2.3 Daily Maximum "Last-in" SWE Files

To produce a time series of continuous, daily, SWE maps for the complete period of record (beginning July 1987 to the present), daily image composites are produced. For all sensors available on a given date, NSIDC1 SWE daily last-in images are combined via pixel-wise maximum (right column, Figure 3). We note that alternative methods could also reasonably be chosen (average, median, etc).

2.2.4 Daily Near Real-Time (NRT) SWE

Daily, near real-time (NRT) CETBv1 data are produced from currently operating SSMIS sensors on DMSP-F16, -F17 and -F18. The SWE "pipeline" (daily and last-in SWE by sensor, and maximum last-in composite) is currently updating the SWE data set. Due to differences in processing schedules for input data to the CETBv1 and processing queues on the CU supercomputer, at the scheduled time of daily processing, the most recent CETBv1 data may be incomplete. Subsequent input data retrievals may retrieve missing swaths from the most recent time periods (the last few days). To ensure that recent gaps and holes are filled in a timely fashion, the nominal daily NRT SWE pipeline is configured to process the most recent 7 days, and to overwrite SWE data files during this recent 7-day period that may have been incomplete at the time of processing on previous days.

Figure 3: Sample NRT SWE output images, 09 Mar 2024. Daily SWE images from the three (DMSP-F16, -F17, -F18) SSMIS sensors operating on this date (left column). Daily composite last-in SWE by sensor (middle column). Note sensor gaps in daily images (left) that are filled in to create last-in SWE images by sensor (middle). Daily maximum last-in SWE from all available sensors (right column).

3 Files

3.1 Input Files

CETBv1 morning pass T_B images from horizontally-polarized 19 and 37 GHz channels are used as daily inputs to the SWE algorithm. Monthly snow climatologies derived from Brodzik and Armstrong (2013) are used to filter false positives. Land cover classifications are masked with Brodzik and Knowles (2011) (Figure 2).

3.2 SWE Output Files

3.2.1 SWE File Contents

Daily and last-in composite SWE files are produced for all sensors available on a given date (see Figure 1 for approximate sensor overlaps), at conventional (25 km) and enhanced resolutions (6.25 km and 3.125 km). Daily maximum last-in composites are produced for each day in the complete time series at conventional (25 km) and enhanced resolutions (6.25 km and 3.125 km), beginning July 1987 and updated daily.

SWE files are formatted as geolocated TIFF (Geotiff), acceptable for ingest to the NSIDC Geoserver Web Coverage Service (WCS). Files include custom metadata fields, prefixed with *CETB_*, for provenance and WCS-ingest related information (Table 2). Each file contains 1 raster "band" *SWE* array, for 1 *EASE-Grid 2.0* projection and spatial resolution.

Table 2: *SWE .tif custom metadata.*

Name	Contents
CETB_DATETIME	Date of coverage, 'yyyy-mm-dd'
CETB_NOMINAL_LTOD	Nominal local-time-of-day, 'yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss', ltod around which morning observations are clustered (Daily: morning ltod; Last-in: ltod of new daily file; Max: average of component file ltods)
CETB_INPUT_FILES	Input files used to create the SWE file (Daily: CETBv1 TB files; Last-In: prior last-in file, new daily file; Max: component last-in files)

SWE data arrays are stored as 2-byte, signed integers, with the following data values:

Table 3: *SWE raster data values.*

Value	Meaning
≥ 7	SWE (mm) on land surface
0	No detectable SWE, land surface (algorithm returned ≤ 7.5 mm)
-150	No available T_B observations, on land surface
-200	Off-grid ("corner") locations; for Northern Hemisphere EASE-Grid 2.0, locations with latitude < 0.0
-250	Ocean
-300	Permanent Ice (Glacier or Ice Sheet) mask

3.2.2 SWE Filename Convention

The SWE .tif filename convention is:

gridName-[platformSensor-]yyydyoy-method-version-algorithm.tif

where parts of the filename are described in Table 4.

Table 4: SWE filename convention.

Part	Description	Values
<i>gridName</i>	EASE-Grid 2.0 grid id	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EASE2_N25km • EASE2_N6.25km • EASE2_N3.125km
<i>platformSensor</i>	Satellite platform and sensor (not used for last_in_max)	See Column 1 of Table ?? One of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F[08 10 11 13 14 15]_SSMI • F[16 17 18 19]_SSMIS
<i>yyyydoy</i>	Date	4-digit year, 3-digit day-of-year
<i>method</i>	Image reconstruction algorithm	one of: GRD or SIR
<i>version</i>	Major.Minor version number of input data files	e.g. v1.5
<i>algorithm</i>	Algorithm ID	NSIDC1_SWE, NSIDC1_SWE.last_in or NSIDC1_SWE.last_in.max
<i>.tif</i>	file format	GeoTiff file formatting

4 Data Access

4.1 Files available via WCS Access

Selected SWE data are available via publicly-accessible GeoServer at:

https://staging.nsidc.org/api/mapservices/CETB_SWE/ows

The GeoServer will respond to WCS queries, e.g. to get the list of coverages (data products), use:

https://staging.nsidc.org/api/mapservices/CETB_SWE/wcs?service=WCS&version=2.0.1&request=GetCapabilities.

To reduce maintenance overhead, the current coverages include daily Northern Hemisphere SWE data from the six historic SSM/I sensors; one SSMIS sensor (DMSP-F19) that operated for a limited period; ongoing SSMIS data from the currently operating F16, F17 and F18; and the daily maximum composites, each at 25 and 3.125 km resolution (Table 5).

Table 5: *List of WCS CoverageIDs.*

CoverageID
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f08_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f08_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f10_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f10_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f11_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f11_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f13_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f13_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f14_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f14_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f15_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f15_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f16_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f16_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f17_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f17_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f18_n25km

CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f18_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f19_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_f19_n3_125km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_last_in_max_n25km
CETB_SWE__nsidc1_daily_swe_last_in_max_n3_125km

To get the list of timestamps (daily resolution), for SWE data:

https://staging.nsidc.org/api/mapservices/CETB_SWE/wcs?service=WCS&version=2.0.1&request=DescribeCoverage&coverageId=COVERAGEID.

A specific data file for a selected coverageID and date can be requested with:

https://staging.nsidc.org/api/mapservices/CETB_SWE/wcs?service=WCS&version=2.0.1&request=GetCoverage&coverageId=COVERAGEID&compression=LZW&cql_filter=timestamp=YYYY-MM-DD

Note that while the timestamps listed in the results for the DescribeCoverage response include default time values of 00:00:00, it is not necessary to include the time as part of the query; if no time is specified, it will default to 00:00:00. Only YYYY-MM-DD is needed.

We have observed that files requested and delivered via the Geoserver interface do not include custom metadata from the source .tif files, regarding file coverage date and provenance. Users wishing to make use of this metadata should use the FTP access method.

4.1.1 WCS Exceptions

The data are stored on a system at the University of Colorado Research Computing facility that performs regular maintenance on the first Wednesday of each calendar month. During maintenance periods, the WCS server will return repeated timeout errors. Maintenance duration is usually 8–12 hours, beginning at 7 a.m. Mountain Time. The status page at:

<https://curc.statuspage.io/>

is a publicly-accessible web page with RC maintenance status information. During maintenance periods, typical responses from the WCS Server will be timeout errors.

Table 6: WCS HTTP Responses.

HTTP Status Code	Response	ows:ExceptionText	Meaning
200 OK		no XML	Success, body of response is tif image (potentially anomalous, data file is completely blank—we are tracking down this condition, potential bug)
200 OK		no XML	
408 Request Timeout			Timeout, potentially due to monthly server maintenance, see status page at https://curc.statuspage.io/ for events affecting CU Petalibrary availability
500 Internal Server Error		Unable to read a coverage for the current request (could be due to filtering or subsetting): org.geoserver.wcs2_0.GridCoverageRequest@ad01a4b4 - exception 500	This error is returned when requested time stamp does not match valid data
500 Internal Server Error		Could not locate coverage nsidc1_daily_swe_f18_n25km	user entered invalid coverageID

4.2 Files available via FTP Access

Data on FTP include all intermediate images, which includes daily SWE and last-in SWE by sensor, and daily maximum last-in composites. All *NSIDC1* SWE data are available via anonymous FTP, at:

```
ftp://dtn.rc.colorado.edu/pl/active/CETB/CETB_SWE
```

The FTP directory hierarchy is:

```
SWElevel/gridName/[platformSensor/]yyyy/
```

where directory levels are described in Table 7.

Table 7: FTP directory hierarchy.

Part	Description	Values
<i>SWElevel</i>	SWE processing level	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CETB_NSIDC1_SWE • CETB_NSIDC1_SWE_last_in • CETB_NSIDC1_SWE_last_in_max
<i>gridName</i>	EASE-Grid 2.0 grid id	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EASE2_N25km • EASE2_N6.25km • EASE2_N3.125km
<i>platformSensor</i>	Satellite platform and sensor (not used for last_in_max)	one of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F[08 10 11 13 14 15]_SSMI • F[16 17 18 19]_SSMIS
<i>yyyy</i>	Year	4-digit year

5 Assumptions/Limitations

The original, 25 km SWE data products were intended for studies of large-scale (continental to hemispheric) seasonal fluctuations of snow cover and SWE. Much of the following section is a summary of known limitations of the original algorithm as defined by Armstrong et al. (2007). The current implementation, using enhanced-resolution data at 6.25 km and 3.125 km, is intended for preliminary evaluation of improvements to the spatial distribution. Due to the lack of in situ validation data for SWE at any of these admittedly coarse spatial scales of the microwave sensors, the magnitude of snow water equivalent derived from satellite passive microwave sensors should be treated as relative rather than absolute indication of SWE values and should always be used with caution. Despite uncertainties in SWE measurements, users find the relative values to be useful climatological information.

When compared with the smoothed 25 km images, the enhanced-resolution (6.25 and 3.125 km) SWE images will likely improve estimates of localized maxima or minima. In general, the enhanced-resolution images will also likely improve the following known limitations of the algorithm when applied at 25 km, and possible undermeasure in the following circumstances:

- Mountainous areas with large topographic variability return low SWE values; 25 km samples from these areas will contain a mixed signal from a large footprint that may include deep snow on north-facing slopes, snow-free south-facing slopes, wind-scoured Alpine areas, etc.
- Forested areas generally return low mean SWE values because the mixed signal includes emission from trees and the snow canopy as well as the underlying surface
- Areas near coastlines return low or no SWE values because the mixed signal includes frozen and unfrozen water and land
- Areas containing melting snow or wet snow packs typical of maritime snow conditions return low or no SWE values because the microwave emission from liquid water overwhelms scattering from the snow pack
- Shallow or intermittent snow during fall and early winter typically does not result in sufficient microwave scattering to reliably detect SWE

Similarly, the enhanced-resolution inputs may improved SWE reliability due to overmeasure, which can occur in areas with significant depth hoar formation. The conditions for depth hoar involve the combination of shallow snow exposed to strong temperature gradients driven by cold air temperatures over a period of weeks to months. This results in a snow cover with large grains that enhance the microwave scattering signal and cause overmeasure when the static algorithm has been tuned to a smaller mean grain size. A typical region prone to this type of snow texture is Eastern Siberia. The seasonal snow cover consistently begins to form in this region as early as September, and then relatively shallow snow remains on the ground as air temperatures begin to approach the extremely

cold conditions of winter. Higher scattering from the large depth hoar grains will return SWE values that are anomalously high.

Over time, the passive microwave-derived SWE values generally indicate greater values for Eastern Siberia than for Western Siberia, although some climate models indicate the opposite. There could be some degree of overmeasure by the microwave algorithm in this region due to the persistent presence of depth hoar.

Lower confidence in SWE reliability due to overmeasure may also occur in areas of extremely high elevation. Current passive microwave snow retrieval algorithms are empirically based and were typically developed using data from lower elevations. (Savoie et al., 2009) investigated an atmospheric correction for regions of extremely high elevation on the Tibetan Plateau, but further work in this direction was not pursued.

There is a persistent pattern of relatively high SWE values that develops during the winter season in a large portion of the Canadian Arctic, stretching roughly from the Western edge of Hudson's Bay to the North Slope of Alaska. Unfortunately, this is an area with few ground observing stations, although a large-scale field experiment begun in the 2003-2004 winter season by Derksen and others (C. Derksen, personal communication, May 2004) indicates that the SWE gradient across this area appears to be real and measurable, if not as large a gradient as the microwave algorithm indicates, and should be treated with caution.

The current implementation does not include a forest correction.

The current implementation uses CETB Version 1.x brightness temperatures (Brodzik et al., 2016), which are derived from CSU FCDR inputs (Berg et al., 2018). For daily NRT processing, the CSU FCDR data latency is usually 2-3 days. The CETB Version 2 brightness temperature record (Brodzik et al., 2023) is currently under production, which uses L1C as an alternative data source (Berg et al., 2018). Data latency for the L1C inputs is shorter, closer to 1 day. When the SWE inputs are switched to Brodzik et al. (2023), the NRT SWE will experience a similar latency improvement.

5.1 WCS Server Limitations

Data delivered via WCS does not include custom metadata fields prefixed with *CETB_* as described in Table 3. Users who require access to this metadata are encouraged to use the FTP access method.

The current WCS server has been successfully tested with several browser clients, and a QGIS client. Similar tests using ArcMap 10.8.2 and ArcPro have not been successful at accessing the daily SWE layers in each of the defined coverages. We have opened a tech support request with ESRI and are actively investigating the reasons for the failure.

6 Acknowledgements

6.1 Funding Resources

This data product has been supported by funding from US Army Engineer Research and Development Center (ERDC). The NSIDC DAAC provides operational funding for the input historical and NRT CETB data.

6.2 Supercomputing Resources

This work utilizes resources from the University of Colorado Boulder Research Computing Group, which is supported by the National Science Foundation (awards ACI-1532235 and ACI-1532236), the University of Colorado Boulder and Colorado State University.

6.3 Software

Software to produce the CETB product includes `cetbtools`, a python package that implements the SWE algorithm for daily SWE images, and the last-in and max-last-in composites. The `cetbtools` software is distributed as a python package via anaconda.org. Source code is licensed under the GNU General Public License v3.0, available at: <https://github.org/nsidc/cetbtools>. Additional processing scripts used to control the historical and daily SWE production are available at https://github.org/nsidc/pmesdr_swe.

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Appendices

A CETB Projections and Grid Dimensions

Data are currently produced in the Northern Hemisphere *EASE-Grid 2.0* projection, at 2 spatial resolutions

Table 8: *CETB product EASE-Grid 2.0 projections and grid dimensions*

Name	Projection	Resolution (km)	Cols	Rows	Latitude Extent	Longitude Extent
EASE2-N25km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	25	720	720	0°–90°	±180°
EASE2-N6.25km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	6.25	2880	2880	0°–90°	±180°
EASE2-N3.125km	Northern Lambert Azimuthal	3.125	5760	5760	0°–90°	±180°

B Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 9: List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AMSR-E	Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer - Earth Observing System
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document
CDR	Climate Data Record
CETB	Calibrated Passive Microwave Daily EASE-Grid 2.0 Brightness Temperature
CF	Climate and Forecast Metadata Conventions
DAAC	Distributed Active Archive Center
dB	decibel
DMSP	Defense Meteorological Satellite Program
EASE-Grid 2.0	Equal-Area Scalable Earth Grid Version 2.0
ERDC	Engineer Research and Development Center
ESDR	Earth System Data Record
FCDR	Fundamental Climate Data Record
GHz	GigaHertz
GMI	GPM Microwave Imager
GPM	Global Precipitation Mission
GRD	(Drop-in-the-bucket) Gridding Method
JAXA	Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency
ltod	Local Time-of-Day
MEaSURES	Making Earth System Data Records for Use in Research Environments
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NSIDC	National Snow and Ice Data Center
NRT	Near real-time
rSIR	Radiometer version of SIR
SIR	Scatterometer Image Reconstruction
SMMR	Scanning Multichannel Microwave Radiometer
SSM/I	Special Sensor Microwave/Imager
SSMIS	Special Sensor Microwave Imager Sounder
T_B	brightness temperature
UCB	University of Colorado at Boulder
